

(REVIEW ARTICLE)

A review on prescription and non-prescription appetite suppressants and evidence-based method to treat overweight and obesity

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Abstract

Shedding pounds isn't simply a question of fitting into a smaller size, it's about your wellbeing. Additional pounds raise your danger of creating interminable and once in a while destructive infection, including stroke, coronary illness, type 2 diabetes, and hypertension. At the point when you are hefty or overweight, you are additionally at a more serious danger of medical problems that meddle with your personal satisfaction, for example, joint pain, sleep apnea, and depression. Appetite suppressants are prescription medications that assist you with controlling your craving, what's more, accordingly your food consumption. Contingent upon the formulation utilized, they may assist you with feeling full sooner. Longings and issues with craving are basic reasons individuals neglect to adhere to a low-calorie weight reduction diet. Appetite suppressants help control your yearning so you can concentrate on giving your body the nutritious food it needs to work ideally as you get in shape and feel better while doing it. Ordinarily, appetite suppressants are used alongside a decreased calorie diet. You receive support and direction with respect to both your medications and your dinner plan at all times. More than 1 in every 3 American grown-ups are overweight or obese. At Weight No More, we need to help decrease this measurement by helping you accomplish a healthy size and a healthy life.

Keywords: Prescription; Non-Prescription; Appetite Suppressants; Overweight; Obesity

1. Introduction

Health care suppliers utilize the Body Mass Index (BMI), which is a proportion of your weight according to your height, to characterize overweight and obesity. Individuals who have a BMI somewhere in the range of 25 and 30 are viewed as overweight. Obesity is characterized by having a BMI of 30 or more notable.^{1,2} You can calculate your BMI if you are overweight or obese. Being overweight or large may build the danger of health issues. Your health care supplier can evaluate your individual hazard because of your weight.³

Obesity is a chronic disease that influences more than one in every three adults in the United States. Another in three adults is overweight. If you are battling with your weight, you may find that a good dieting arrangement and standard physical movement help you with getting more fit⁴ and keep it off for a long haul. On the off chance that these way of life changes are insufficient to assist you with getting in shape or keep up your weight reduction, your primary care physician may prescribe medications as a feature of your weight-control program.^{5,6}

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Appetite suppressants are drugs that stunt the body into trusting it isn't ravenous. Medications delegated appetite suppressants follow up on the body's central nervous system, fooling the body into accepting that it isn't ravenous. Some examples of remedy appetite suppressants include: benzphetamine, diethylpropion, mazindol, and phentermine. These medications are generally available as tablets or extended delivery capsules. Appetite suppressants can be endorsed or bought over-the-counter.⁶ Appetite suppressants are utilized as a transient treatment for patients with weight. It is not unexpected to feel hungry. It is your body's method of revealing to you that it is an ideal opportunity to fuel up. Be that as it may, on the off chance that you end up wanting food despite the fact that you just ate, there's a decent possibility you'll put on weight.⁷

2. Classifications of appetite suppressants

- Prescription appetite suppressants
- Nonprescription appetite suppressants

2.1. Prescription appetite suppressants

Appetite suppressants are drugs designed to control hunger and, thusly, assist you to get in shape.^{9,11} The FDA has endorsed these medications that you can get just get with a Doctor's solution.

2.1.1. *Liraglutide*

Also called Saxenda. You take this as an injection. Additionally, it was featured as a diabetes treatment under the brand name Victoza. The medication alleviates hunger by following up on a hormone in the intestine.⁸

2.1.2. *Naltrexone*

It contains two medications and can influence the reward framework in your brain, so eating certain foods that would regularly cause you feel great do not do anymore.¹⁰ It also works on the hypothalamus, the part of your brain that manages appetite, temperature, and different capacities.¹²

2.1.3. *Phenteramine*

Also called Qsymia. It's a combo of two medications. Phentermine is a stimulant that causes you to feel less hungry.¹³ Topiramate is a medication utilized for seizures and migraine, however as a component of a combo with phentermine may cause you to feel not so much hungry but rather more full. There are likewise some different choices - like phentermine, benzphetamine, diethylpropion, and phendimetrazine - yet those must be utilized for as long as 12 weeks.¹⁴

2.2. Nonprescription appetite suppressants

Hunger suppressants check your hunger and prevent you from gorging. Here are six characteristic hunger suppressants that you can remember to keep your eating regimen on target.

2.2.1. *Fenugreek*

Fenugreek is a spice that has a place with legumes family. The little yellow seeds, which are generally utilized in Indian food for including flavor are additionally known for its medicinal properties. The seeds contain 45% fiber, which is for the most part insoluble. The fiber hinders the procedure of carb and fat absorption in the body,¹⁵ saving your fuller for a more drawn-out time. Having fenugreek seeds are viewed as valuable in bringing down blood pressure.^{16,17}

- How to have it

You can straightforwardly chew one teaspoon of these seeds two times every day or absorb 1 teaspoon of the seeds a glass of water for the time being and drink it the morning.

2.2.2. *Green tea extract*

Green tea extract is an incredible fat eliminator and appetite suppressant. It contains two significant mixes, which help in the weight reduction process-caffeine and catechins. Studies recommend that catechins additionally help to support digestion, which is urgent when you plan to shed kilos.¹⁸

- How to have it

Have 200-250 ml of green tea twice day by day for compelling outcomes.

2.2.3. Almonds

Nuts are constantly considered excellent tidbits to control your mid-afternoon hunger aches. In any case, almonds should be your preferred choice when you need to avoid binge eating.¹⁹ Loaded with fiber, almonds are a rich source of antioxidants, vitamin E and magnesium, which helps to suppress your affluent hunger. They increase the feeling of fullness.²⁰

- How to have it

Have a bunch of almonds when you feel hungry.

2.2.4. Ginger

We as a whole love the kind of ginger in our tea and dishes, however, this herb makes them flabbergast medicinal properties. It stimulates your digestive system, can ease nausea and can likewise suppress your appetite.²¹ According to a little 2012 investigation, men who expended ginger at breakfast felt more full for at any rate 3 hours after their dinner.²²

- How to have it

You can have ginger tea or even have ginger enhancements after consulting your primary care physician.

2.2.5. Yerba mate

Yerba mate is a native plant of South America. It is regularly used to make a drink called mate. The beverage is known for its energy stimulating and appetite stifling properties. It hinders the procedure of stomach purging, which keeps you from careless eating.

- How to have it

You can either take yerba mate in powdered form or have supplements or have yerba mate tea twice daily.²³

2.2.6. Coffee

Because of the high caffeine content, coffee is not viewed as useful for wellbeing. In any case, when we talk about weight reduction it very well may be very useful. Coffee diminishes your hunger, expands calorie consumption and fat breakdown. These things can be gainful when trying to shed kilos.²⁴ Yet, by coffee, we mean dark coffee, not the standard one weighed down with sugar and milk.²⁵

- How to have it

Have 200-250 ml of coffee twice daily. Due to the high caffeine content, coffee is not viewed as useful for wellbeing. Yet, when we talk about weight reduction, it very well may be very advantageous. Coffee diminishes your hunger, expands calorie consumption and fat breakdown. These things can be helpful when attempting to shed kilos.²⁶

3. Mechanism of action

Centrally acting appetite suppressant drugs utilized in the treatment of weight loss in two broad pharmacological classifications; those that demonstrate through cerebrum catecholamine pathways and those which demonstration by means of serotonin pathways.²⁷ Of the previous gathering, amphetamine and phenmetrazine are no longer suggested in view of their energizer properties and addictive potential. The rest of the medications in this class incorporate amfepramone (diethylpropion),²⁸ phentermine, mazindol, and phenylpropanolamine. All have been shown to decrease craving and lower food consumption, subsequently helping obese patients more effectively maintain a low-calorie diet and get fitter.²⁹

4. Appetite suppressant works?

Indeed, however likely not as much as you would trust. A review of studies on five significant FDA-approved prescription medications for obesity, including orlistat, shows that any of them work better than a placebo for helping individuals lose at any rate 5% of their body weight through the span of a year. Phentermine-topiramate and liraglutide had the most notable chances of getting that going.³⁰

It is additionally imperative to comprehend that these medications do not take a shot at their own. Studies show that weight reduction medication, including appetite suppressants, work best when you're additionally rolling out solid improvements to your eating and exercise propensities simultaneously.³¹

5. When appetite suppressants are included in weight loss plan?

In the event that you've just battled with weight reduction for a considerable length of time, appetite suppressants might be a piece of your underlying arrangement. Be that as it may, if this is your first endeavor at weight reduction, we will sit back and watch how much weight you lose over a couple of long periods of following an eating routine and exercise plan.

Similarly, there are clinical rules overseeing the use of appetite suppressants. These proposals depend on your weight file (BMI), which mirrors the measure of muscle versus fat you convey. On the off chance that your BMI is 25-29.9, you're overweight. Any worth that is at least 30 is viewed as obese.³²

Prescription appetite suppressants are suggested for patients who meet two rules. You're a decent applicant in the event that you have a BMI of 27 or higher and you're determined to have at any rate one weight-related ailment, for example, hypertension or Type 2 diabetes.³³ You can likewise get the medication if your BMI is more than 30, with or without other medical issues.

Settling on a choice about utilizing an appetite suppressant isn't simply founded on your BMI. We will likewise think about your general wellbeing and check whether there is any explanation why the medication may not be ok for you. For instance, appetite suppressants may interface with different medications you take. You additionally shouldn't take them in case you're pregnant or plan to get pregnant.³⁴

6. Benefits of using prescription medication to lose weight

At the point when joined with changes to behavior, including eating and physical movement propensities, prescription medications may assist some with people to lose weight. Weight loss of 5 to 10 percent of your beginning body weight may help improve your wellbeing by bringing down glucose, pulse, and fatty substances. Additionally, getting in shape can improve some other medical problems associated with overweight and obese, for example, joint disease or sleep apnea. Most weight loss happens inside the initial a half year of beginning the medication.³⁵

7. Tips for taking weight loss medication

- Adhere to your doctor's instructions about weight reduction medications.
- Purchase your medication from a pharmacy or web distributor endorsed by your doctor.
- Take weight reduction medication to help your healthy eating and physical activity program.³⁶
- Know the side effects and warnings before taking any medicine.
- Inquire if you should quit taking your medication in the event that you do not getting thinner following 12 weeks.
- Talk about different medications, including supplements and vitamins, you are taking with your doctor when considering weight-loss medications.
- Abstain from taking weight loss medications during pregnancy or on the occasion that you are planning a pregnancy.³⁷

8. Evidence-based methods to suppress appetite

8.1. Eat more protein and fortifying fats

Not all nutrients satisfy hunger similarly. Contrasted with sugars, proteins and certain fats are more powerful for fulfilling craving and keeping individuals feeling full for more. An individual can replace a few wellsprings of sugar with proteins and invigorating fats to help monitor their craving. The accompanying high-protein nourishments are lean meats, eggs, beans, and peas, soy items, and Greek yogurt.

8.2. Drink water before each entry

Drinking a huge glass of water legitimately before eating has been found to cause an individual to feel more full, more fulfilled, and less ravenous after the supper. Another investigation, which took a gander at hunger in 50 overweight females, indicated that drinking 1.5 liters of water a day for about two months caused a decrease in craving and weight, and furthermore prompted more noteworthy fat misfortune. A soup starter may likewise extinguish the appetite.³⁸ Research from 2007 indicated that individuals revealed feeling fuller following the supper on the off chance that they had a fluid starter.³⁹

8.3. Eat all the more high-fiber foods

Fiber does not separate like different nourishments, so it remains in the body for more. This hinders assimilation and keeps people feeling full for the duration of the day. Exploration proposes that fiber can be a compelling appetite suppressant. High-fiber eats less carbs are likewise connected with lower corpulence rates. Then again, another audit found that bringing additional fiber into the eating regimen was viable in less than half of the investigations they delved into. More exploration is expected to recognize which sources of fiber are the best for smothering appetite.⁴⁰ Healthful high-fiber nutrients incorporate entire grains, beans, and heartbeats, apples and avocados, almonds, chia seeds, and vegetables.⁴¹

8.4. Exercise before a meal

Exercise is another viable and sound hunger suppressant. An audit dependent on 20 distinct examinations found that hunger hormones are stifled following activity, particularly high-force workouts.⁴² They discovered lower levels of ghrelin in the body, a hormone that makes us hungry, and more significant levels of "completion hormones, for example, PYY and GLP-1.^{43,44}

8.5. Drink Yerba Maté tea

Examination shows that a tea called Yerba Maté, which originates from the *Ilex paraguariensis* plant, can diminish hunger and improve mind-set when joined with high-power work out. Yerba Maté is available for buy on the web.

8.6. Switch to dark chocolate

Dark chocolate has been shown to suppress appetite compared to milk chocolate. One study showed that people ate less during their next meal after snacking on dark instead of milk chocolate.⁴⁵

Eat some ginger

Consuming a small amount of ginger powder has been shown to reduce appetite and increase fullness, possibly due to its stimulating effect on the digestive system. This was a small-scale study⁴⁶, so more research is needed to confirm this effect. Ginger powder is available for purchase online.⁴⁷

8.7. Eat bulky low-calorie foods

Reducing general food intake while dieting can leave people with a ravenous appetite. This can cause a relapse into binge eating. However, dieting does not have to mean going hungry. Some foods are high in nutrients and energy but low in calories. These include vegetables, fruits, beans, and whole grains. Eating a large volume of these foods will prevent the stomach from growling and still allow a person to burn more calories than they consume.⁴⁸

8.8. Stress less

Comfort eating due to stress, anger, or sadness is different from physical hunger. Research has linked stress with an increased desire to eat, binge eating, and eating non-nutritious food. Mindfulness practices and mindful eating may

reduce stress-related binge eating and comfort eating, according to a research. Regular sleep, social contact, and relaxation time can also help tackle stress.⁴⁹

8.9. Mindful eating

The brain is a major player in deciding what and when a person eats. If a person pays attention to the food they are eating instead of watching television during a meal, they may consume less. Research published in the journal *Appetite* found that eating a huge meal in the dark led people to consume 36% more. Paying attention to food during meals can help a person reduce overeating. Another article showed that mindfulness might reduce binge eating and comfort eating, which are two significant factors that influence obesity. The National Institute of Health recommends using mind- and body-based techniques, such as meditation and yoga, to curb appetite.^{49,48}

9. Conclusion

Researchers are as of now studying a few new medications and combination of medications in animals and individuals. Researchers are attempting to recognize safer and more viable medications to help people who are overweight or corpulent lose weight and keep up a healthy weight for quite a while. Future medications may utilize new methodologies, for example, to combine medications that influence appetite and those that influence enslavement craving, stimulate gut hormones that lessen appetite, shrink the blood vessels that feed fat cells in the body, along these lines keeping them from developing, target genes that influence body weight, change microscopic organisms in the gut to control weight.

Compliance with ethical standards

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The authors confirms that there is no conflict of interest.

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